

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING SWIMMING TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Menglikulov Khayrulla Alikulovich

Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Sports Activities and Management
Termez State University

Annotation: Swimming, playing and having fun on the water are one of the most useful types of physical exercise that contribute to the health of children: they strengthen their nervous system, muscular frame and contribute to the development of the musculoskeletal system and the ability to control it. Therefore, in kindergarten, during swimming lessons, health promotion is a priority.

Key words: modular equipment, swimming, preschool age; innovative methods, teaching methods, methodological techniques.

Introduction. The physical development of preschool children is the basis for comprehensive development [3, 5]. During the period of preschool childhood, a child develops the basic skills for developing health conservation, and as researchers note, this is the most favorable time for developing the right habits, which, in combination with teaching preschoolers how to improve and maintain health, will lead to positive results [1, 2, 6].

One of the most important ways for children to develop physically and improve their health is swimming. Swimming, playing and having fun on the water is one of the most useful types of physical exercise that contributes to the health of children and strengthens their nervous system [4, 7]. Therefore, the sooner you accustom a child to water and teach him to swim, the more fully the positive impact of swimming will have on the development of the entire child's body [9, 11].

In this regard, the main objectives of the learning process are:

- development of swimming skills;

- nurturing in children persistent motivation for health and a healthy lifestyle based on their acquisition of knowledge about the priority of health and the mechanisms of vital activity of the human body;
- strengthening and protecting the physical health of children.

Before moving directly to the disclosure of the practical work of a physical education instructor, it is necessary to dwell on such concepts as “method” and “innovation”.

Methods are often understood as a set of ways, methods of achieving goals, and solving educational problems.

The term “innovation” first appeared in scientific literature in the 19th century and meant the introduction of certain elements of one culture into another. This meaning has been preserved to this day in ethnography. Pedagogical innovation processes have become the subject of special study by scientists since about the end of the 50s of the 20th century in the West and in the last decade of the 21st century in our country. It is worth noting that today, despite the active study of this phenomenon, in the specialized literature there is confusion in such concepts as “new”, “innovation”, “innovation process”, which are not as simple and unambiguous as this may seem at first glance.

In the scientific literature, innovation is defined as a purposeful change that introduces new stable elements (innovations) into the implementation environment, causing a transition of the system from one state to another [10, 12, 13].

Any innovation is associated with an update. However, not everything new gives positive results everywhere and always due to the following reasons:

- something new is not always a means of solving problems that are relevant for a particular institution;
- each new tool is born in very specific conditions and is focused on solving very specific pedagogical problems, which may not coincide with the personal tastes and interests of the heads of the institution;

- each new pedagogical tool has a technological side associated with the specifics of its use, and a personal one, allowing the specialist and the head of the institution to influence the effectiveness of its development by demonstrating their individual qualities (professional preparedness, sociability, emotionality, charm).

In kindergarten, during swimming lessons, the health-improving focus is a priority and, solving the main task - ensuring the full physical development of children, we have set ourselves the goal of optimally increasing the degree of health improvement of pupils, considering the pool as one of the main health-improving procedures in a unified system of children's health improvement in preschool educational institution [14, 15, 18].

Swimming is considered a complex skill that requires separate practice of each swimming element: holding the breath, diving, ascent, lying, sliding, arm work, footwork, proper breathing. To acquire it, the method of repeated swimming exercises in water is used, which is a combination of the studied exercises.

Methods of teaching swimming are divided into three groups: visual, verbal and practical. Visual methods create a clear picture of the subject being studied. They are practically implemented by demonstrating swimming methods and various exercises (this requires a good demonstrator, preferably a peer who is fluent in these movements or actions), as well as showing photographs, drawings, posters, and toys [16, 17].

Verbal methods include explanations, stories, comparisons, comments, instructions, orders, commands, counting, analysis (for older preschool age).

When working with children of primary preschool age, verbal methods must be intelligible and easy to understand: it is necessary to use comparisons with movements and actions known to the child.

Practical methods are methods of exercise, studying movements in general and in parts, competitive, control [19, 20].

In this hierarchy of methods of teaching swimming, the leading place is occupied by the game method. Games, as a rule, should contain swimming elements

previously learned by children and various preparatory exercises for swimming. Simple and accessible didactic aids, varied in form and purpose, should be used in training. Mastering various movements occurs by repeating them many times. The number of repetitions should increase gradually. Considering that repetition of movements is a monotonous activity and tires children, they should be offered a variety of exercises in one lesson.

So, the innovative methods used in kindergarten for classes on land are:

- elements of yoga in physical education classes for preschool children (children's yoga is different in that all exercises are performed in a playful way);
- musical-rhythmic exercises in teaching swimming to preschoolers; rhythmic refers to health-improving types of gymnastics and includes physical exercises that are simple in technique (general developmental, dance), performed to emotional rhythmic music;
- systematic rhythmic classes increase children's motor activity, develop the ability to coordinate and coordinate movements with the tempo and rhythm of music, provide an opportunity to express their individual characteristics through movements, and help navigate space;
- funk aerobics - this type of activity is characterized by a special movement technique: springy walking, freer hand movements, emphasis on danceability and emotionality of movements.

In kindergarten, during swimming lessons for preschool children, in addition to standard sports equipment, modular equipment is used to attract children's attention, create an emotional background for the lesson and interest in them, as well as a desire to overcome emerging difficulties and have fun. For this purpose, a significant number of various exercises are used on modules, which make it possible to correctly feel the position of the head, arms, and movements in the hip joint.

Such equipment:

- stimulates and enriches the motor activity of children;
- develops and improves movements;

- allows you to solve a wide variety of problems in class;
- promotes the development of a sense of balance and correct posture;
- Helps children gain confidence and independence.

It is especially important when learning to swim to demonstrate exercises performed in the water. Children do not always immediately learn the correct execution of a new movement, so it needs to be demonstrated many times, both in one and over several lessons. It is best to demonstrate the exercises immediately before performing them, performing all movements correctly, clearly, easily, without tension. The demonstration must be accompanied by a story, conversation, explanation, and timely remark accessible to children, which stimulate purposeful, conscious mastery of movements.

Conclusions. The results of our work indicate that the volume of physical activity and its subsequent increase and complexity are within the power of children and help to gain confidence in their abilities and develop children's swimming skills.

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